

A Comparison of Different Theories of Viscous Flow for Binary Molten Electrolytes

A. P. SRIVASTAVA

Department of Chemistry, National Post-Graduate College,
Barhalganj, Gorakhpur-273 402

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It appears from literature that the theoretical evaluation of viscosity in binary liquid mixtures has been a subject of active interest in the last few decades. Several empirical and semi-empirical relations^{1,2} for viscosity have been proposed. Several workers have evaluated different interaction parameters using viscosity measurement³⁻⁵. Pandey and Chaturvedi⁶ furnished data over wide range of composition and temperature. Advancement in the research of transport properties of molten salts have been made in these years. Zuca *et al.*^{7,8} have carried out the experimental determination of viscosity of binary halides and nitrates, some attempts to viscosity predictions for molten alkali halides have been made either theoretically or empirically^{9,10}.

Recently¹¹, the viscosity of binary liquid mixtures of toluene with chlorobenzene, benzyl alcohol and n-hexanol has been evaluated using Frankel, Naidu, Hind, Grunberg-Nissam and Katti-Chaudhuri's theories. The aim of present investigation is to extend different theories of viscous flow of binary liquid mixtures to binary mixtures of molten halides as they may be considered as ionic liquids. The theoretical results are compared with experimental findings and the result has been discussed in terms of intermolecular interaction.

Theoretical :

Frankel¹² obtained the following relation for the theoretical value of viscosity of binary liquid mixtures,

$$\log \eta_m = X_1 \log \eta_1 + X_2 \log \eta_2 + 2X_1 X_2 \log \eta_{12} \quad (1)$$

where, η_1 and η_2 are viscosities of pure liquids at mole-fractions X_1 and X_2 , respectively, η_m is viscosity of the mixture, and η_{12} , the mean viscosity, is given by

$$\eta_{12} = 0.5\eta_1 + 0.5\eta_2 \quad (2)$$

Hind *et al.*¹³ and Naidu¹⁴ used the following expressions for the viscosity of a binary mixture, respectively,

$$\eta_m = X_1^2 \eta_1 + 2X_1 X_2 \eta_{12} + X_2^2 \eta_2 \quad (3)$$

$$\ln \eta_m = X_1^2 \ln \eta_1 + 2X_1 X_2 \ln \eta_{12} + X_2^2 \ln \eta_2 \quad (4)$$

η_{12} in equations (3) and (4) is the same as in equation (2). The expression for viscosity as given by Grunberg and Nissam¹⁵ is

$$\ln \eta_m = X_1 \ln \eta_1 + X_2 \ln \eta_2 + X_1 X_2 d \quad (5)$$

where, d is the approximate measure of strength of interaction and is given by

$$d = - \left[\frac{1}{X_1 X_2} \cdot \frac{\alpha' \Delta F_m}{RT} \right] \quad (6)$$

In equation (6), $\alpha' \Delta F_m$, the excess free energy of mixing, is related to viscosity of mixture as

$$\alpha' \Delta F_m = -RT[\ln \eta_m - \ln \eta_1] \quad (7)$$

$$\text{and} \quad \eta_{12} = X_1 \eta_1 + X_2 \eta_2 \quad (8)$$

Katti-Chaudhuri¹⁶ obtained the following relation for evaluation of viscosity,

$$\begin{aligned} \ln \eta_m \times V_m \\ = X_1 \ln \eta_1 V_1 + X_2 \ln \eta_2 V_2 + X_1 X_2 \frac{W_{vis}}{RT} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

In equation (9), W_{vis} is interaction energy and V_m is molar volume. W_{vis} is related to molar volume by the relation,

$$X_1 X_2 \frac{W_{vis}}{RT} = \ln \frac{V_m}{X_1 X_2} + X_1 X_2 d \quad (10)$$

Results and Discussion

The molar volume (V_m), excess free energy of mixing ($\alpha' \Delta F_m$) from equation (7), strength of interaction (d) from equation (6) and interaction energy (W_{vis}) from equation (10) for KCl+NaCl system at 1 200 and 1 220 K, and for KBr+KCl system at 1 073 and 1 173 K are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—MOLAR VOLUME (V_m), $\alpha' \Delta F_m$, d AND W_{vis} FOR BINARY MIXTURES OF ELECTROLYTES

Temp. K	x_1	V_m cm ³ mol ⁻¹	$\alpha' \Delta F_m$ cal mol ⁻¹	d	W_{vis} cal mol ⁻¹
KCl+NaCl					
1 200	0.152 3	41.272	113.63	-0.369 1	-749.43
	0.348 5	43.730	180.43	-0.333 3	-687.54
	0.570 0	47.041	186.66	-0.323 6	-615.52
	0.792 5	49.448	183 15	-0.467 1	-979.52
1 220	0.152 3	41.584	-111.40	0.855 9	981.08
	0.348 5	44.604	87.56	-0.159 0	-143 93
	0.590 0	47.418	142.17	-0.244 1	-424.36
	0.792 5	49.850	177.03	-0.444 1	-923.18
KBr+KCl					
1 073	0.200 0	55.672	1.186 2	-0.003 4	-1.933
	0.400 0	54.046	0.400 7	-0.000 7	-6.408
	0.500 0	53.295	0	0	15.744 6
	0.800 0	50.884	2.884 7	-0.008 4	-13.321 9
1 173	0.200 0	58.018	1.103 0	-0.002 9	18.742 5
	0.400 0	57.063	2.215 3	-0.003 9	142.206 5
	0.500 0	54.650	0	0	-115.639 6
	0.800 0	52.950	1.675 6	-0.004 4	13.580 0

The necessary data required for calculation have been taken from literature^{9,17}. The viscosity of the aforesaid mixtures evaluated by the methods of

TABLE 2—EXPERIMENTAL AND THEORETICAL VALUES OF VISCOSITY FOR BINARY MIXTURES KCl+NaCl

Temp. K	x_1	η_{exp} C.P.	η_m O.P. (eq. 1)	η_m C.P. (eq. 3)	η_m C.P. (eq. 4)	η_m C.P. (eq. 5)	η_m C.P. (eq. 9)
1 200	0.000 0	0.951	—	—	—	—	—
	0.152 3	0.888	0.901 6	0.931 3	0.830 8	0.886 8	0.896 8
	0.348 5	0.840	0.855 8	0.906 0	0.905 0	0.838 0	0.834 3
	0.590 0	0.809	0.823 2	0.874 8	0.879 7	0.806 9	0.799 3
	0.792 5	0.786	0.814 3	0.848 7	0.848 0	0.784 6	0.666 9
	1.000 0	0.822	—	—	—	—	—
1 220	0.000 0	0.852	—	—	—	—	—
	0.152 3	0.886	0.807 2	0.846 2	0.846 2	0.885 9	0.885 8
	0.348 5	0.809	0.771 9	0.838 7	0.838 7	0.817 3	0.808 7
	0.590 0	0.782	0.759 3	0.829 5	0.829 5	0.781 3	0.781 7
	0.792 5	0.764	0.773 9	0.821 8	0.821 8	0.763 9	0.768 8
	1.000 0	0.814	—	—	—	—	—

x_1 = Mole-fraction of KCl.

TABLE 3—EXPERIMENTAL AND THEORETICAL VALUES OF VISCOSITY FOR BINARY MIXTURES KBr+KCl

Temp. K	x_1	η_{exp} C.P.	η_m O.P. (eq. 1)	η_m O.P. (eq. 3)	η_m O.P. (eq. 4)	η_m O.P. (eq. 5)	η_m O.P. (eq. 9)
1 073	0.000 0	1.093	—	—	—	—	—
	0.200 0	1.078	1.097	1.078 6	1.078 3	1.077 5	1.077 5
	0.400 0	1.064	1.092	1.064 2	1.063 2	1.062 8	1.063 3
	0.500 0	1.057	1.086	1.057 0	1.056 6	1.056 8	1.056 3
	0.800 0	1.034	1.036	1.035 4	1.035 1	1.033 5	1.033 5
	1.000 0	1.021	—	—	—	—	—
1 173	0.000 0	0.849	—	—	—	—	—
	0.200 0	0.815	0.789	0.815 4	0.845 4	0.845 0	0.844 9
	0.400 0	0.841	0.774	0.841 8	0.841 8	0.841 0	0.840 9
	0.500 0	0.840	0.769	0.840 0	0.840 0	0.840 0	0.839 9
	0.800 0	0.834	0.789	0.834 6	0.834 6	0.834 0	0.833 9
	1.000 0	0.831	—	—	—	—	—

x_1 = Mole-fraction of KBr.

Frankel (equation 1), Hind *et al.* (equation 3), Naidu (equation 4), Grunberg – Nissam (equation 5) and Katti – Chaudhuri (equation 9) are reported in Tables 2 and 3. The experimental viscosity for comparison are also included in the Tables. Table 2 indicates that for NaCl+KCl system, Grunberg – Nissam and Katti – Chaudhuri relations give values more comparable with the experimental values than other three methods, whereas Table 3 reveals that there is excellent agreement between the experimental and theoretical values for KCl+KBr system at all the temperatures and all the mole fractions by all the aforesaid methods.

The values of d and W_{vis} based on interaction energy are very small for KCl+KBr system (Table 1), hence there is no difference in theoretical values of viscosity in the methods of Grunberg – Nissam and Katti – Chaudhuri (which include interaction energy) and the other three methods. This contention receives support from the study of conductivity and molar volume for this system⁶. The viscosity isotherm of KCl+KBr system predicts that the system is particularly ideal from the thermodynamic point of view¹⁸. The difference in the theoretical values of viscosity by the methods of

Grunberg – Nissam and Katti – Chaudhuri and that of Frankel, Naidu and Hind *et al.* is due to greater values of d and W_{vis} for KCl+NaCl system. This difference also shows deviation from ideality.

On the basis of the above discussion it may be concluded that all the aforesaid expressions (equations 1, 3, 4, 5 and 9) can very well be applied to molten salts and their binary mixtures for the evaluation of viscosity.

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same reaction when carried out with allyl bromide, 10-allylacridone (**2**; 35%) m.p. 129°, was obtained along with unreacted acridone (~30%).

Thioacridone when refluxed in dry acetone/potassium carbonate with propargyl bromide and allyl bromide under nitrogen atmosphere furnished 9-acridyl propynyl thioether (**3a**) and 9-acridyl allyl thioether (**3b**; 70–72%) (Scheme 1). Usually the thioethers of acridine are prepared by complementary reaction^{20, 21} of 9-chloroacridine with simple arylmercaptans or sodium salt of alkylmercaptans.

Scheme 1 Reagents: (1) RBr, acetone/K₂CO₃.

Alkylation of Acridone and Thioacridone

S. K. CHATTOPADHYAY, B. K. SEN

and

K. C. MAJUMDAR*

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani,
Kalyani-741 235

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EXTENSIVE studies^{1–11} concerning acridone derivatives have lately been carried out mainly on account of their established therapeutic properties but most of the methods employed for their synthesis required the use of strong bases like sodamide⁹, sodium ethoxide¹⁰, powdered potassium hydroxide^{1, 11} etc. Recently, much interest has been shown on the alkylation of acridone and thioacridone using phase transfer catalysis^{12–16} and these again provide confronting reports^{12, 13, 17}.

During our studies on the alkylation of anthrone with allyl bromide and propargyl bromide¹⁸ via aromatisation of the acidic benzenoid system, we became interested in the alkylation of acridone and thioacridone using milder condition especially to find a way to avoid isomerisation of the propynyl group during alkylation¹⁸. In this note, we report the results of alkylation of thioacridone and acridone with propargyl bromide and allyl bromide in acetone/potassium carbonate, a versatile alkylation medium¹⁹.

Acridone when treated with propargyl bromide in refluxing dry acetone and anhydrous potassium carbonate for 24 h, acridone (~30%) was recovered along with a white crystalline solid (35%), m.p. 211°. It was characterised as 10-propynylacridone (**2a**) from its elemental analysis and spectral data (vide Experimental) and no isomeric ynamine was obtained. The

All melting points are uncorrected. Elemental analyses and spectral measurements were obtained from R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow.

10-Propynylacridone (2a): A solution of propargyl bromide (0.011 mol) in dry acetone (25 ml) was added to a mixture of acridone (0.01 mol) and potassium carbonate (2 g) in dry acetone (50 ml) and the mixture was refluxed with stirring for 24 h. The mixture was cooled, filtered and the solvent removed in vacuum. The residual mass was extracted with chloroform and the chloroform extract was washed with brine and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of solvent gave a crude solid which was purified by chromatography (silica gel column). Elution with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°)–benzene (1 : 1) gave a white crystalline solid (**2a**; 0.80 g, 35%), m.p. 211° (Found: C, 82.2; H, 4.6. C₁₆H₁₁NO requires: C, 82.4; H, 4.7%) $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 660 (C=O), 2 130w and 3 200s cm⁻¹ (C≡CH); δ (CDCl₃, 90MHz) 2.35–2.45 (1H, t, due to C≡CH), 4.95–4.99 (2H, d due to NCH₂), 7.15–7.30 (2H, m), 7.50–7.75 (4H, m) and 8.40–8.50 (2H, m); m/z 233 (M⁺, 100%), 232, 204, 194 and 166.

10-Allylacridone (2b) was similarly prepared, (35%), m.p. 135° (lit.^{9–11} 132° prepared by using powdered KOH) (Found: C, 81.4; H, 5.4. C₁₆H₁₃NO requires: C, 81.7; H, 5.5%) $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 670, 1 590, 1 500 and 1 450 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃, 60MHz) 4.80–5.00 (2H, d), 5.20–5.50 (2H, t), 5.90–6.30 (1H, m), 7.30–8.00 (6H, m) and 8.50–8.80 (2H, m).

9-Acridyl propynyl thioether (3a): To a refluxing mixture of thioacridone (0.01 mol) and potassium carbonate (2 g) in dry acetone (50 ml) under nitrogen atmosphere was added a solution of propargyl bromide (0.011 mol) in dry acetone (25 ml) and the refluxing was continued for additional 4 h. Usual workup of the reaction